

DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIDIMENSIONAL ASSESSMENT ON DEPRESSION FOR PARENTS

Michelle Abella-Cellona, RPsy, PhD

*Psychology Area, Cebu Institute of Technology-University, Cebu City, Cebu,
Philippines*

MindProCebu Psychological Services, Cebu City, Cebu, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the development of a tool aimed at assessing depression among parents, filling a crucial gap in mental health evaluation tools. Through meticulous research and analysis, the inventory was crafted to evaluate the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral manifestations of depression, capturing the condition's complexity in the parental context. Utilizing Cronbach's alpha, the study assessed the internal consistency and reliability of the inventory, yielding excellent reliability scores (0.904 for cognitive, 0.927 for emotional, and 0.923 for behavioral domains). These findings underscore the inventory's robustness and efficacy in consistently measuring parental depression. Additionally, the tool demonstrated stability, indicating each item's significant contribution to the overarching construct without adversely affecting the scale's reliability. The implications of this study are multifaceted, providing a reliable instrument that can be integrated into various settings for the early detection and intervention of parental depression. This advancement is pivotal in potentially mitigating the negative impact of parental depression on family dynamics. Recommendations emphasize the need for broader validation studies, the application of the inventory in diverse settings, and its incorporation into mental health and parental support programs. The study highlights the critical role of reliable, accessible, and culturally sensitive tools in understanding and supporting parents with depression, aiming to enhance mental health outcomes for families.

Keywords: *Parental depression, Depression inventory, Mental health assessment, Cronbach's alpha, Reliability, Emotional manifestations, Cognitive manifestations, Behavioral manifestations, Early detection*

INTRODUCTION

Depression among parents has emerged as a significant concern, particularly accentuated by the challenges brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic. Research spanning from the global context to specific insights from the Philippines underscores the profound impact of parental depression on both individual and familial well-being. Internationally, studies have sought to unravel the complex factors contributing to parental depression, including the stress of balancing work and family life, the isolation from lockdowns, and anxieties about health and economic uncertainties. For instance, Cameron et al. (2020) examined the heightened risk of depression among parents during the pandemic, emphasizing the need for accessible mental health services. Similarly, Racine et al. (2021) highlighted the disproportionate impact of pandemic-related stressors on mothers, pointing to the importance of targeted support. Further research by Silverio et al. (2021) explored the role of social support in mitigating depression effects among new parents, while Liu et al. (2021) investigated the long-term consequences of parental depression on child development. O'Connor et al. (2021) also provided insights into effective screening and intervention strategies.

In the Philippines, the mental health landscape for parents during the pandemic was explored by Hechanova et al. (2021), who revealed significant stressors that contribute to depressive symptoms and emphasizing the importance of support from the community and family. The synthesis of recent research on depression among parents, both globally and within the Philippines, illuminates a critical gap in mental health support and intervention strategies. Studies have highlighted the multifaceted nature of parental depression, exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, revealing an urgent need for targeted mental health interventions and support systems. However, a recurring theme across these studies is the challenge of effectively identifying and assessing depression among parents, a crucial step towards providing timely and appropriate care. This challenge underscores the necessity of developing a comprehensive tool to assess parents' depression, tailored to capture the unique experiences and stressors faced by parents today contributing to depressive symptoms and the crucial role of community and family support. Additionally, Labrague (2021) examined the psychological impact of the pandemic on Filipino nurses, many of whom are parents, highlighting the dual burden of healthcare work and parenting responsibilities.

These studies collectively emphasize the complex and multifaceted nature of parental depression, drawing attention to the exacerbated challenges faced during the pandemic and the vital role of support systems and interventions. By examining the latest research, this introduction sets the stage for further exploration into effective strategies

for preventing and treating parental depression, with the ultimate goal of fostering healthier families and communities globally and within the Philippines.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the reliability and validity of the newly developed depression inventory in assessing depression among parents. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of reliability of the depression inventory in measuring the depression manifestations of parents in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive,
 - 1.2. emotional, and
 - 1.3. behavioral?
2. What recommendations may be forwarded for the improvement of the mental health of parents particularly in handling depression?

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants of this study were the parents of the enrolled students at the two HEIs of Cebu City. They consist of 192 males (27.54%) and 505 females (72.46%) with a mean age of 41.19. It was conducted on the day the respective institutions held a parents' workshop on mental health. The workshop was facilitated by a Registered Psychologist and was assisted by guidance counselors, principals, teachers, psychometricians, and psychology interns.

Procedure

The HEIs where the study was conducted, respectively, had workshops about mental health for their institutions. They were held on different dates. During the registration and ushering of the participants, the tool and instructions were given to them. They were informed of the option of wanting to answer the survey or not.

Guidance counselors, teachers, and psychology student interns were strategically assigned within the venue to assist the participants with their concerns or clarifications.

The researcher then prepared the inventory to identify the level of stress of the research participants. An informed consent form was stated at the bottom page of the instrument for the research participants to sign should they agree to participate in the research conducted. An appointment was set with the guidance counselors of the two participating HEIs of Cebu City. The questionnaires were given to each department for review and reproduction.

Before the start of the workshop, a one-hour ushering-in activity was done, where participants were given the instruments and instructions. Guidance counselors, teachers,

and psychology interns were strategically situated in the venue to assist at least 5-7 parents, making sure that someone would answer their questions or clarifications. Once the questionnaires were given to them, the consent forms were cut off and gathered, but they were placed separately to further keep the answers random and confidential.

All the questionnaires were then collated into one population. Each statement of the inventory and its corresponding answers were then tallied to produce their frequency and percentage in the population. The researcher then clustered the statements into tables that showed similarities in nature and labeled it with its respective theme.

Instrument

The Depression Inventory is a self-report tool used to gauge levels of depression of parents. A 4-point anchored scale is used to rate the frequency of each manifestation within a fourteen-day timeframe with 0 for Not at all, 1 for Less than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (1-6 days), 2 for More than half of the number of days in 2 weeks (7-13 days), and 3 for Always (Everyday). These constructs assessed various manifestations such as cognitive, emotional and behavioral.

Scoring

Each statement in the inventory is scored based on how strongly the manifestations were felt during a specific period. A score of 0 indicates that the manifestations were not felt at all, while a score of 3 indicates that they were felt every day. Total scores were summed up to get the mean score and were classified as either No, Low, Moderate, and High.

Content Validity of the Instrument

In the development of the inventory, the crucial role of content validity was highlighted, emphasizing its necessity for tests to comprehensively cover the constructs they are designed to for depression. This entails a detailed verification process, often requiring consensus among experts for thorough evaluation (Nikolopoulou, 2023). To ensure the assessment tool's relevance, clarity, and comprehensive coverage of the intended construct, an initial review of the items was conducted by experts in psychology, parenting, and psychometrics. Moreover, the qualitative phase of the study utilized a content analysis approach, incorporating semi-structured, in-depth interviews with three psychologists and two psychometrists, all with significant experience in working with parents within their psychological practice. This expert feedback proved instrumental in refining the inventory, guiding the revision, addition, and deletion of items to enhance the instrument's content validity. Such a process was pivotal in ensuring that the inventory accurately reflects the domain of depression among parents, thus making it a valid tool for assessing this specific psychological construct.

Pilot Testing

To ensure the questionnaire really captures what it's meant to, we tested a first version with a small group of 10 parents, split evenly between men and women. This test helped us see if the questions were clear and if the questionnaire was easy to use.

Data Treatment

To evaluate the internal consistency or reliability of the questionnaire items, Cronbach's alpha was employed. This method involves assessing the shared variance or covariance among the items within the instrument compared to the total variance observed. The underlying principle is that a higher covariance among the items, relative to the overall variance, signifies a reliable instrument. Essentially, Cronbach's alpha calculates the average of all possible split-half reliabilities, providing a standardized measure of agreement between the items on a scale from 0 to 1. Higher Cronbach's alpha values suggest a higher level of agreement among the items, reflecting consistency in participants' responses across a set of questions. This consistency is crucial for the development and evaluation of new survey instruments. A Cronbach's alpha threshold of 0.7 was established as a benchmark for sufficient consistency, indicating that the measure is reliable. While values around 0.7 are considered minimally acceptable, they are not ideal; conversely, excessively high values may suggest redundancy among the questions.

RESULTS

In order to assess the reliability of the statements in the inventory, it applied Cronbach's alpha as a key metric, which is still used in present studies (Amirrudin et al., 2020). This was used as it has been seen as a fundamental tool to evaluate internal consistency or reliability of the measurement scale employed within the research framework (Goforth, 2015). It aimed to gauge the interrelatedness of the items, showing its consistency to measure the expected construct.

Depression Inventory

Table 1.1 Cognitive Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.904
95% CI lower bound	0.893
95% CI upper bound	0.915

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
D5	0.896
D6	0.891
D7	0.907
D8	0.895
D9	0.896
D15	0.896
D20	0.895
D25	0.892
D27	0.890
D31	0.891

Table 1.1 shows the statistical reliability of the instrument in assessing the cognitive manifestations of depression among parents. The Cronbach's α , is 0.904, which is considered 'excellent.' This suggests that, overall, the items within the scale provide a consistent and dependable measure of cognitive manifestations. Furthermore, the 95% confidence interval (CI) for the scale's reliability spans from 0.893 to 0.915, indicating a high level of confidence in the consistency of the measurements obtained. Additionally, the individual item reliability statistics display the Cronbach's α values if each respective item were hypothetically excluded from the scale. The values for each question go from 0.890 to 0.907 which implies that even if we remove any one statement from the inventory, it won't make the tool much less reliable. So, the tool remains stable and reliable in measuring parental depression through cognitive manifestations. Items in this instrument to test this aspect included Statement 6 "I think people don't mind my existence", Statement 15 "I have thoughts that I would be better dead or hurt myself in some way", and Statement 31 "Negative thoughts kept haunting me especially when I'm alone or at night". These were seen as relevant in testing as they were also findings in other literature.

Table 1.2 Emotional Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.927
95% CI lower bound	0.918
95% CI upper bound	0.935

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
D1	0.919
D2	0.921
D3	0.919
D4	0.919
D12	0.920
D13	0.922
D14	0.930
D17	0.922
D21	0.920
D22	0.920
D29	0.920
D30	0.923
D32	0.920

Table 1.2 shows reliability of the items in assessing the emotional manifestations of depression among parents. The scale's reliability, evaluated using Cronbach's α , showcases an impressive level of internal consistency, with a point estimate of 0.927, denoted as 'Excellent.' This score signifies a robust and dependable measure of the construct being evaluated, indicating strong coherence among the items in the scale. The values between 0.918 and 0.935 tell us the range of how reliable the statements are. The lower values under 'If item dropped' indicate the potential impact on test reliability in the event that one statement is eliminated. They are all roughly comparable to the mean, indicating that the tool remains valid for measuring parent's emotional manifestations of depression. Sample statements to check on the emotional manifestations of parents included Statement 3 "There's emptiness in my heart", Statement 17 "I feel like the world is better without me", and Statement 30 "I am sensitive to other people's comments about me". These were some of the collated manifestations that have been found across different literature, such as those done by Grahek et al. (2019) and Berry's (2022).

Table 1.3 Behavioral Manifestation Statements Reliability Statistics (Cronbach Alpha)

Frequentist Scale Reliability Statistics	
Estimate	Cronbach's α
Point estimate	0.923
95% CI lower bound	0.915
95% CI upper bound	0.931

Note. Of the observations, pairwise complete cases were used.

Frequentist Individual Item Reliability Statistics	
Item	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
D11	0.918
D16	0.921
D18	0.915
D19	0.917
D23	0.916
D24	0.915
D26	0.915
D28	0.917
D33	0.915
D34	0.919
D35	0.917
D36	0.918

Table 1.3 presents reliability statistics pertaining to the tool focusing on behavioral manifestations. The primary metric used for gauging the internal consistency and reliability of the assessment, Cronbach's α , is reported as 0.923, signifying an excellent level of reliability. The confidence interval (CI) provides a range within which the true reliability of the test is likely to lie, with the lower bound at 0.915 and the upper bound at 0.931, indicating a high degree of confidence in the test's consistency. The subsequent section details the impact of removing each individual item from the assessment on its overall reliability. These values, ranging from 0.915 to 0.921, demonstrate the potential effect of eliminating specific statements. Notably, these values remain close to the primary reliability metric, suggesting that removal of any single item would have a minimal impact on the overall reliability of the test in assessing behavioral manifestations among parents. To check on the parents' behavioral manifestations, the statements such as Statement 16 "I inflict pain to myself when in difficult situations", which was still found in Cipriano et al.'s (2017) paper, Statement 24 "I feel tired most of the time", and Statement 34 "I acquire physical absences than usual in school/work", if which were also seen in Corfield et al.'s (2016) study and Fletcher's (2022) article, were included.

The results of applying Cronbach's alpha scores to each statement in the inventory show a high degree of reliability and internal consistency. The determined Cronbach's alpha scores were within the acceptable range, demonstrating a high degree of consistency and interrelatedness across the questions that measure the stress, anxiety, and depression that parents encounter. Therefore, these reliable indicators offer a strong basis for precisely assessing and understanding the complex sensations of stress, anxiety, and depression in parents.

DISCUSSION

The results from the analysis of the developed inventory to assess depression among parents highlight its strong reliability across cognitive, emotional, and behavioral manifestations of depression. The high Cronbach's alpha values observed in Table 1.1 ($\alpha = 0.904$), Table 1.2 ($\alpha = 0.927$), and Table 1.3 ($\alpha = 0.923$) indicate an 'excellent' level of internal consistency for each domain assessed by the inventory. These values, well above the commonly accepted threshold for reliability, affirm the tool's efficacy in providing consistent and dependable measurements across different dimensions of parental depression.

The 95% confidence intervals further reinforce the reliability of the inventory, with narrow ranges indicating a high level of precision in the instrument's ability to measure the intended constructs. Specifically, the confidence intervals for cognitive (0.893 to 0.915), emotional (0.918 to 0.935), and behavioral (0.915 to 0.931) manifestations underscore the robustness of the scale in capturing the nuanced aspects of depression among parents.

Moreover, the analysis of individual item reliability, indicated by the slight changes in Cronbach's alpha values if items were removed, showcases the stability of the inventory. Each item contributes meaningfully to the overall construct measurement, with no single item disproportionately affecting the scale's reliability. This suggests a well-balanced tool where each question plays an integral role in capturing the breadth of parental depression's cognitive, emotional, and behavioral facets.

These findings collectively highlight the inventory's strong psychometric properties, making it a valuable instrument for accurately assessing and understanding the complex phenomenon of depression among parents. The high degree of reliability and internal consistency across different manifestations of depression provides a solid foundation for further research and practical applications in mental health assessment and intervention for parents experiencing depression.

Conclusions

The comprehensive analysis of the newly developed inventory for assessing depression among parents has demonstrated excellent reliability across cognitive, emotional, and behavioral domains, as evidenced by Cronbach's alpha values. The instrument's robust internal consistency, coupled with narrow confidence intervals, ensures its effectiveness in capturing the multifaceted nature of parental depression with precision and stability. Furthermore, the individual item reliability analysis underscores the balanced contribution of each item to the overall construct, highlighting the tool's capacity to remain reliable even with the potential removal of individual statements. These findings affirm the inventory's validity and reliability as a psychometrically sound tool, poised to significantly contribute to the accurate assessment, understanding, and intervention of depression among parents, thereby addressing a critical need in mental health research and practice.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the current study, several recommendations can be made to further the research and application of the developed inventory for assessing depression among parents:

1. **Further Validation Studies:** Although the inventory has shown excellent reliability, it is recommended to conduct further validation studies involving larger and more diverse populations. This could include parents from various socio-economic backgrounds, ethnicities, and parenting situations (e.g., single parenting, parents of children with special needs) to ensure the tool's applicability across different demographics.
2. **Longitudinal Research:** Implementing longitudinal studies to track changes in parental depression over time using the inventory can provide insights into how depression manifests and evolves in parents. This can also help in understanding the long-term efficacy of interventions aimed at reducing parental depression.
3. **Cross-Cultural Adaptation and Validation:** To enhance the inventory's global applicability, adapting and validating it for use in different cultural contexts is recommended. This involves ensuring that the inventory's items are culturally sensitive and relevant, thereby making it a valuable tool for international research and practice.
4. **Integration into Clinical Practice:** Healthcare providers, especially those in pediatric and family medicine, should be encouraged to use the inventory as part of routine screenings for parental depression. This can facilitate early identification and intervention, contributing to better mental health outcomes for parents and their families.
5. **Development of Intervention Programs:** Based on the insights gained from the inventory application, develop targeted intervention programs tailored to the specific needs of parents exhibiting signs of depression. These programs can focus on cognitive-behavioral strategies, social support enhancement, and stress management techniques.
6. **Educational Campaigns:** Launch educational campaigns aimed at raising awareness about parental depression, its impact on family dynamics, and the importance of seeking help. These campaigns can also highlight the availability of the inventory as a self-assessment tool for parents to recognize symptoms of depression early.

To support the local government units (LGUs) in addressing parental depression effectively, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Implement Community Screenings: Incorporate screenings for depression among parents into existing health services at community centers and barangay health stations. Utilize the developed inventory for early detection to connect parents with the support and resources they need.
2. Educate and Empower: Offer training for barangay health workers and community volunteers on recognizing signs of depression in parents and basic mental health support strategies. Promote awareness through community seminars and online platforms to destigmatize seeking help for mental health issues.
3. Create Support Networks: Establish support groups and wellness programs for parents within the community, focusing on stress management, emotional well-being, and parenting support. Collaborate with mental health professionals to provide expert advice and counseling services.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All applicable institutional guidelines where the study was conducted were followed. The participants were informed of their freedom to answer the survey instrument. All who had submitted their answers had written informed consent.

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